

Political Power of The People in Vietnam

Tran Thi Thu Huong

Main lecturer, Tran Thi Thu Huong

ABSTRACT

The category of political power is of great interest to politicians, but up to now, the concept of political power still has many different opinions. From a personal point of view, the article points out political power and political power in Vietnam, and at the same time points out that political power belonging to the people in Vietnam is exercised in all areas of life. Then propose solutions to strengthen the guarantee that political power belongs to the people in Vietnam.

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INTRODUCTION

When human society appeared, classes and society divided into the ruling class and the ruled class, the category of political power was of great interest to thinkers and philosophers on both sides of the globe. theoretical and practical aspects in order to build a society with good and humane community relations, ensuring the rights, obligations, and development ability of each individual. The study of political power to clarify the political power belongs to the people in Vietnam and propose some solutions to strengthen the assurance of political power belongs to the people in Vietnam is a necessary issue in the current period of time great today.

CONTENT

Political power and political power in Vietnam

Politics in the most general sense is an activity field of social life, including activities and relationships among subjects in social life related to the identification and resolution of problems, common to the whole society, especially the contentious issues, common conflicts in social relationships [1]. To be able to solve the above problems, a common power is established with coercive power to maintain order, peace and justice in society, and ensure the rights and freedoms of citizens.

Political power is the right to decide and decide important political affairs, to organize and operate to ensure the power to exercise that power of a class, a political party, or a social group in order to win political power or maintain the right to lead, decide, run the state apparatus, govern a society [1].

Political power appears when society is divided into classes and there are antagonistic class conflicts in society [2], which is reflected in the state's concentration. The class that wields political power is usually also the class that holds economic power. Political power is the concentrated expression of economic power. Political power can belong to a political party of a class, a coalition of many parties or to the people, when the ideals of the class or the political party are suitable, serving the common interests of the whole community nation.

In today's Vietnam, political power belongs to the people, which is concentrated in state power under the leadership of the Communist Party of Vietnam, the vanguard of the Vietnamese working class, loyal representatives of the right to power, interests of the working class, the working people and the whole nation.

Political power in Vietnam is exercised by the state apparatus, which is the agency and instrument of political power. The state centralizes political power. Through the state, political power that belongs to a part of the population becomes a public power for the whole society, because the state is the official representative of the whole society, in the name of society to administer, manage and command the whole society. In order to perform its role and fulfill its mission, the state established a professional apparatus to manage all areas of social life, bringing society to operate according to a certain line and policy. The tools of force and coercion such as courts, prisons, police, army... to ensure the implementation of their policies and laws, and in the name of the whole society to issue a system of rules of conduct for the whole society to follow, bringing the activities of the whole society to operate in a certain direction. The State is

capable of mobilizing through tax policies, the contribution of the whole society, creating a financial basis for the organization and operation of the state apparatus in the implementation of State policies.

Political power belongs to the people in Vietnam

Political power belonging to the people is an objective trend in the Vietnamese revolutionary process

The working people are the basic factor in the productive force, the one who directly creates material and spiritual wealth for the society, the decisive force for the development of society.

Political power belongs to the people, that is, the people own and control economic, political, cultural and social power, and use political power to secure and enforce the interests of the people, benefits in the process of existence and development.

In Vietnam, "All state power belongs to the people" has been affirmed in Article 2 of the revised Constitution approved by the XIII National Assembly at its sixth session. This is the continuation of the Party and State's consistent stance on upholding people's sovereignty and affirming that "the Socialist Republic of Vietnam is owned by the people".

The August Revolution of 1945, under the leadership of the Communist Party of Vietnam, led by President Ho Chi Minh, our people stood up for independence and liberated the nation from the French colonial yoke, Overthrew the feudal system and established the Democratic Republic of Vietnam. As the subject of the national liberation revolution, our people have regained power into their own hands, are the masters of society, this is the source of power - power originates from the people. , belongs to the people. Since then, has officially formed and established a new perspective on people's power in Vietnam's political history - political power of the people.

The political power of the people is realized through the Constitutions of our country. After taking power, the historical task of the Democratic Republic of Vietnam state is to "preserve the territory, gain complete independence and build the nation on the basis of democracy". In the first Constitution of 1946, we advocated the implementation of "strong and wise government of the people" in order to unite the whole people, regardless of race, sex, class, religion, ensuring the rights of the people democratic freedoms. Political power belongs to the people or the people are the subject of political power, which has been clearly expressed in the first legal document - the people are the supreme subject of power, the people authorize and empower them part of its power for the state to exercise through state institutions. But this does not equate people's power with state power. The people also never give all their power to the state, still retain the right to decide on important issues of the nation and nation.

On the basis of the view that the political power of the people was established in the 1946 Constitution, the 1959 Constitution continued to affirm and clarify the view that the origin of state power originates from the people's power. With the epistemological logic that power belongs to the people, the people are the organizers of their State, so the institutions directly established by the people should be the institutions that exercise state power. Therefore, Article 4 of the 1959 Constitution stipulates: All power in the Democratic Republic of Vietnam belongs to the people.

The view of political power belonging to the people was continued in the 1980 Constitution. Still following the logic of the 1946 Constitution and the 1959 Constitution, Article 6 of the 1980 Constitution affirms: "In the Socialist Republic of Vietnam, Nam, all power belongs to the people."

The 1992 Constitution, amended and supplemented in 2001 on the issue of people's power and state power, the division, coordination and control among these powers has been generalized into a general view: "The State The Socialist Republic of Vietnam is a socialist rule of law state of the people, by the people and for the people. State power is unified, with assignment and coordination among state agencies in the exercise of legislative, executive and judicial powers [3].

The socialist rule of law state of the people, by the people and for the people has affirmed that all state power belongs to the people, the people are the organizers of their State.

Thus, firstly, with the view of state power - a kind of political power that always belongs to a class or an alliance between classes - in the current conditions in our country, the Communist Party of Vietnam is the most powerful force in the world. The sole leader of the State and society, therefore, the organization and exercise of state power are all under the leadership of the Party. It is this that determines the unity of state power - the political unity of state power.

Second, from the social aspect of the matter, state power belongs to the people. The people are a unified whole that includes all ethnic groups, classes, and classes living and working in the Vietnamese territory, so their power is unified and not divided. The unity of state power is the unified expression of power belonging to the people and from the very nature of the State - social institutions, institutions created by society. It is society that creates the State, not the State.

Currently, our country is in the transition to socialism, all political power belongs to the People. But the People only directly exercise certain powers such as: The right to stand for election, to vote, to exercise the rights to life, freedom, democracy, the right to study and travel, etc. such as: The right to mobilize and allocate all resources for the cause of national construction and defense; the right to manage and administer the society; the right to manage economic development and cultural development; the right to uniformly manage and administer the cause of security and national defense..., the People give it to agencies and organizations established and elected by the People, and even the People empower a group, even will be given to an individual representative of the People to perform. Organizations, groups of people, and individuals empowered by the People to properly perform, perform well, and effectively perform their assigned responsibilities and tasks, for the people, for the sake of the country, bring many benefits to the country, for the people and for the country.

The people are the subject of political power over all areas of social life

In our country today, the political power of the people is gradually established in all areas of social life.

The field of politic

First, the people have the right to a truly democratic state. That state is elected by the people, the state is the instrument to exercise the people's legitimate powers. The state is placed under direct control and through representative organizations of the people. People have the right to trust or not trust a part of state agencies.

Second, the people have the right to participate in State affairs. The people have the right to discuss all matters large and small that are directly related to their legitimate interests. With that in mind, people's rights are not only exercised through representative institutions, but also through direct democracy, but the general trend is that direct democracy will increase. That is the level of expression of the advanced level in the people's exercise of their political power. The people's power in the political field is also meaningful within the limits of the political monism, ensuring to maintain the socialist orientation, on the basis of Marxism-Leninism and Ho Chi Minh's thought. Minh serves as an ideological foundation, ensuring for all people the right to freedom of thought, freedom of speech, and freedom of belief within the framework of the law. It is also the right to supervise the activities of the State and the political system.

The field of economy

Building an economy based on public ownership of the main means of production of the whole society to meet the increasing development of the productive forces on the basis of modern science and technology to satisfy increasingly satisfy the material and spiritual needs of the entire working population. In order to do this, it is necessary to stabilize politics, develop production and improve the living standards of the whole society, under the leadership of the Communist Party and the management, guidance and assistance of social states, tenet.

First, ensure the people's right to master the main means of production; the right to master in the process of production, business, management and distribution, must consider the economic interests of workers as the most basic driving force for socio-economic development.

Second, it is necessary to consider the socialist economy as the successor and development of all the achievements that mankind has created in history, and at the same time filter out the backward, negative, restraining factors... of the socialist economy, previous economic regimes, especially the nature of private ownership, oppression, and unfair exploitation... for the majority of the working people, thereby forming the public ownership of the means of production, abolishing unjust oppression and exploitation.

Third, to build a socialist-oriented market economy with many forms of ownership and economic sectors, in which the state economy plays the leading role, the private economy is the driving force. importance of the economy; subjects of all economic sectors are equal, cooperate and compete according to the law; the market plays a key role in effectively mobilizing and allocating development resources, which is the main driving force to release productive power; State resources are allocated according to strategies, master plans and plans in line with the market mechanism, creating a developed economy, which is an important condition and premise for the people to exert their power, their politics and actualize their power in real life.

Fourth, the economy must be linked with society, unifying economic policies with social policies, economic growth must go hand in hand with the implementation of social progress and justice right in each step, each policy and throughout. In the process of development, only then will the people have the conditions and promote their mastery in the economic field.

The field of culture - society

In order for the people to exercise their political power, it is necessary to take Marxism-Leninism, the ideology of the working class, as the mainstream for all other forms of social consciousness in the new society. At the same time, it inherits and promotes the quintessence of traditional culture.

Solutions to strengthen the assurance that political power belongs to the people

The field of political problems

Firstly, improving the class and revolutionary nature of the political system: Ensuring the people's power is a self-conscious process of the Communist Party implemented by the State and socio-political organizations. association under the leadership of the Communist Party.

To do this, it is necessary to:

Build a contingent of cadres and party members who are passionate about ideals and wholeheartedly serve the people. In our country today, in the conditions of the market economy and opening for integration, a large number of cadres and party members are degrading in moral ideology, degenerating, corrupt, wasteful and become criminal. The deterioration in politics, morality and lifestyle has led to a departure from the Party's principles and the State's laws, causing discontent and frustration in society, and reducing the economy and trust, of the people towards Party and State organizations. Therefore, it is necessary to build a team of party members who are passionate about ideals, wholeheartedly serving the Fatherland, serving the people.

Party building must be associated with state building and a clean and strong political system. Because only when the State is strong and upright, the Vietnam Fatherland Front and socio-political organizations strongly promote their roles, functions and tasks can they put forward guidelines and policies of the Party into life. Likewise, the Party and State can only be strong and fulfill their tasks when and only when the Vietnam Fatherland Front and socio-political organizations fully promote their roles and responsibilities, specifically: transform the guidelines and lines of the Party, policies and laws of the State into practical actions of the people, demonstrating the people's right to mastery and protecting the legitimate rights and interests of the people promote the people's mastery in all fields, including politics.

Second, it is necessary to build a real democracy, where all powers belong to the people. The people must really be the subject of society, and moreover, the people must be fully mastered: the master of the state, the master of the society, and the master of himself, the master and possessor of all powers, their creative power as the true subject of society. On the other hand, the people's right to mastery must cover all areas of socio-economic life, from democracy in economy, democracy in politics to democracy in society and democracy in life. Cultural, spiritual and ideological, in which the two most important and prominent fields are democracy in economy and democracy in politics.

Third, renovate the organization and mode of operation of the political system to ensure democracy for the people.

On organizational reform and the Party's leadership method, we need to:

Raise awareness and properly perform the role of the political nucleus and the leadership level of the Party organizations at all levels in order to promote the organization's initiative, creativity and sense of responsibility in the political system, in the political system implementation of the Party's line.

Renovate the Party's leadership method needs to raise awareness and have the right conception of the Party's comprehensive leadership. The first is the renewal, the making of resolutions and directing the implementation of the Resolutions of the Party. Promoting democracy in Party activities, maintaining unity and unity within the Party. Strengthen inspection, strictly implement the principle of democratic centralism and working regulations; strengthen education and training to improve revolutionary morals and qualities for cadres and party members.

To renovate and improve the efficiency of State management, we need to:

Strongly promote the role of the state government system in the expansion and implementation of democracy, perfect the democratic mechanism, well implement the grassroots democracy regulation, concretize the motto that the people know, the people table, the people do, people check.

Take care of building and consolidating the entire State apparatus from the central to grassroots level, with compact structure, efficient operation, a contingent of qualified, capable, qualified and responsible cadres high. The operation of State agencies must put the task of serving the people first, and properly and quickly solve problems directly related to the people's lives. Educating State cadres and civil servants to build and practice the style of "Truly respecting the people, being close to the people, understanding the people, studying the people and being responsible to the people", "Listening to the people, speaking to the people, understanding, making the people believe"

Develop mechanisms and measures to inspect, control, prevent and punish bureaucracy, corruption, abuse of power, and violations of the people's right to mastery; prevent and overcome the situation of formal democracy and extreme democracy, and at the same time strictly punish disruptive activities...

Strictly implement the principle of democratic centralism in the organization and activities of the State apparatus. In order to renovate and consolidate socio-political organizations, we should:

- Raise awareness of the whole society about the position and role of the Fatherland Front and socio-political organizations.
- Promote and improve the quality of activities of mass organizations and organizations

The field of Economic problems

Perfecting the economic institution, putting the economy under the control of the people, serving the people's legitimate needs and interests.

To form an economic mechanism so that all employees can participate in ownership and management in various forms.

Combining the strict plan of the State with promoting the initiative of enterprises and employees.

The market must be a place to compete on the principle of value, on the basis of quality to ensure the interests of consumers.

The field of culture - ideology

Ensure citizenship, human rights and social protection rights of citizens, gradually overcome differences between social classes and regions of the country; step by step liberate people from inhuman relationships.

Maintaining the socialist orientation, taking Marxism-Leninism and Ho Chi Minh's thought as the ideological foundation, a guideline for all actions, firmly protecting the revolutionary achievements that the people have created in the past, history of the nation.

CONCLUSION

The political power of the people is expressed as the right to have a State guarantee for the people as the subject of political power in order to exercise the rights and interests of the people when they participate in the political life. At the same time, this is a deeply humane element that demonstrates the people's mastery over all areas of social life, the result of the struggle towards happiness, freedom, true democracy for people.

In order for political power to belong to the people, to the people, for the people in Vietnam, it is necessary to have an enforcement mechanism. Those are the principles, organizational methods, management measures and activities of the Communist Party, the Socialist State, and socio-political organizations that put the people's political power values into practice practical political life.

REFERENCES

1. Ho Chi Minh National Academy of Politics (2006), Political Lectures,
2. Vietnamese Wikipedia, Political Power (<https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki>)
3. Prof. Dr. Ta Ngoc Tan (2021), Some issues of controlling political power in our country today, website of the Central Theoretical Council on February 7, 2021(<http://hdl.vn/en/nghien-cuu---trao-doi/mot-so-van-de-ve-kiem-soat-quyen-luc-chinh-tri-o-nuoc-ta-hien-nay.html>)